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MODERN APPROACHES TO THE MANAGEMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CLOSED ABDOMINAL TRAUMA

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ANNOTATION

In this article presents modern approaches to the use of operations performed by traditional and laparoscopic methods for closed abdominal injuries. The general conditions of conservative treatment of closed abdominal injuries are indicated. The possibilities of modern endovideosurgery for closed abdominal injuries are described in detail.

Keywords: abdominal injury, laparoscopy, diagnosis.

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ВЕДЕНИЮ БОЛЬНЫХ С ЗАКРЫТОЙ ТРАВМОЙ ЖИВОТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлены современные подходы к применению операций, выполняемых традиционными и лапароскопическими способами при закрытых травмах брюшной полости. Указаны общие условия консервативного лечения закрытых травм живота. Подробно описаны возможности современной эндовидеохирургии при закрытых травмах брюшной полости.

Ключевые слова: травма живота, лапароскопия, диагностика

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ҚОРИННИНГ ЁПИҚ ШИКАСТЛАНИШЛАРИДА БЕМОЛЛАРНИ ОЛИБ БОРИШ БЎЙИЧА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада қориннинг ёпиқ шикастланишларида анъанавий ва лапароскопик усулда бажарилган операцияларни қўллашдаги замонавий ёндашувлар ёритилган. Консерватив даволашнинг умумий шартлари кўрсатиб ўтилган. Замонавий эндовидеохирургиянинг имкониятлари батафсил ёритилган.

Таянч сўзлар: қорин ёпиқ шикастланиши, лапароскопия, диагностика.

Introduction

In the historical aspect, the views on the management of patients with closed abdominal trauma are radically changing from the tactics of mandatory laparotomy in the presence of clinical and ultrasound signs of intra-abdominal injuries to the tactics of conservative (non-surgical) treatment of certain categories of victims. Today, non-surgical treatment of patients with abdominal trauma under the condition of stable hemodynamics is becoming more widespread all over the world and shows high efficiency in the range of 80-90% [48]. Conservative management of victims selected according to strict indications helps to reduce the frequency of exploratory (in fact, futile) laparotomies and is considered the safest choice in large trauma centers, where surgeons on duty, operating units, intensive care units (ICU) and other support services operate around the clock. Nevertheless, conservative tactics are fraught with the risk of late diagnosis of intra-abdominal injuries, especially in cases of damage to hollow organs, the diaphragm and two-stage ruptures of parenchymal organs [46].

The main motivation for expanding the tactics of non-surgical management of patients with abdominal trauma was data on the frequency of exploratory laparotomies, especially in patients with penetrating wounds of the anterior abdominal wall, which, according to the established canons of surgery, are one of the main indications for laparotomy and revision of abdominal organs. According to various authors, the frequency of futile laparotomy in patients with wounds and blunt abdominal trauma reaches 25-40%. Moreover, this indicator is significantly higher (75-80%) with penetrating wounds of the lumbar region compared with wounds of the anterior abdominal wall (15-27%) [28].

Obviously, the high frequency of unnecessary laparotomies increases the cost of treatment and the number of complications. So, back in 1951, a report was published on 5 cases of death in children after splenectomy [32].

After such cases, some surgeons began to limit the indications for splenectomy for spleen injuries, especially in children. In 1984, the results of conservative treatment of a ruptured spleen in CAT were published, according to which the effectiveness of this approach was 30%, and the mortality rate was 12.3%, mainly due to severe traumatic brain injury [40]. In 1989 T.H.Cogbill et al. [22] published the results of a multicenter study on the experience of conservative treatment of closed spleen injury, where the effectiveness of treatment in adults was 83%, and in children – 98%. More up-to-date data also indicate a high efficiency, reaching 95%, of conservative management tactics for patients with ruptured spleen [33].

The first report on the results of conservative treatment of liver ruptures was published in 1979 [36]. Subsequently, A.A.Meyer et al. [39] pointed to the advantage of computed tomography in the selection of patients with closed liver injury subject to conservative management. In their opinion, patients without CT signs of deep damage to the liver parenchyma, with a hemoperitoneum volume of no more than 250 ml or without a shock clinic are not shown laparotomy. Currently, there are more and more supporters of conservative tactics for the treatment of closed liver injuries of any degree in patients with stable hemodynamics, the effectiveness of such tactics is 90-95% [1,15]. A significant increase in the effectiveness of non-surgical treatment of abdominal injuries was facilitated by the active introduction of interventional radiology methods, especially when performing endovascular hemostasis in patients with bleeding fractures of the pelvic bones, ruptures of the liver and/or spleen, damage to the main vessels [3,20,50].

Taking into account the increasing interest of specialists in the non-surgical treatment of abdominal injuries, the International Consensus Conference in 2018 formulated this tactic as "the primary non-surgical strategy for the treatment of parenchymal organ injuries, which usually consists of observation, but may include the use of endovascular, percutaneous or endoscopic procedures" [18]. The basis of non-surgical treatment of damage to parenchymal organs of the abdominal cavity is hemostatic therapy and drugs aimed at stimulating healing and preserving the function of injured organs. Although there are convincing data on the effectiveness of non-surgical treatment of shallow ruptures of parenchymal organs, such as liver, spleen, pancreas and kidneys, nevertheless, caution is recommended when using this tactic in patients with intestinal wall hematoma, severe pancreatic ruptures, penetrating wounds of the kidney and spleen. Important conditions for the non-surgical tactics of managing patients with abdominal trauma are the round-the-clock availability of emergency

surgery and the possibility of continuous intensive monitoring. In patients selected for non-surgical treatment, it is mandatory to conduct a CT study with contrast enhancement to identify damaged organs and assess the severity of the damage [38].

In addition to the points that limit the widespread use of non-surgical tactics, there is a fairly wide list of unresolved issues that require study and consensus: 1) how often and for how long is it necessary to conduct blood tests and repeated ultrasound / CT of the abdominal cavity? 2) when is it better to resume oral intake of fluids and food? 3) what is the duration of strict bed rest? 4) when is it better to start drug prevention of venous thromboembolism? 5) the optimal period of the patient's stay in the hospital? Against the background of uncertainty in the issues of conservative treatment of patients with abdominal trauma, laparoscopy is becoming increasingly common in various urgent surgical diseases of the abdominal cavity, including abdominal injuries. The main generally recognized advantages of using laparoscopy are the possibility of reducing cases of "exploratory" laparotomy and the duration of inpatient treatment of patients with abdominal wounds [14], however, there are still disputes regarding the indications and therapeutic possibilities of laparoscopy [33]. If in the first publications there were concerns that laparoscopic diagnosis is fraught with a certain number of cases of missed intra-abdominal injuries, then in subsequent reports, as more clinical experience of using this technique is accumulated, researchers increasingly began to emphasize the accuracy of laparoscopy in the diagnosis of abdominal injuries with penetrating abdominal wounds [41]. There are separate reports of the use of therapeutic laparoscopy for injuries of the diaphragm, liver, spleen and hollow organs [2,7,19].

Currently, laparoscopic technique has taken a firm place in the "planned" surgery of the abdominal cavity and retroperitoneal space and does not cause much discussion in terms of indications and the degree of effectiveness. Continuous improvement of video endosurgical technology (increasing the resolution of the video camera, development and introduction of new stitching devices and electrosurgical devices that provide more reliable and safe hemostasis and tissue dissection), significant improvement in the experience and skills of laparoscopic surgeons contributed to the expansion of the scope of laparoscopic surgery, reducing the frequency of conversion of these interventions in trauma. These trends are reflected in recent publications. If the publications of the end of the last and the beginning of this century more often covered the issues of diagnostic laparoscopy [4,27,49], the reports of recent years demonstrate the high effectiveness of therapeutic laparoscopy, which covers procedures such as hemostasis, suturing and resection of the intestine, restoration of the bladder, splenectomy, distal resection of the pancreas, suturing of a diaphragm defect, etc. [5,7,8,33,40].

The wide possibilities and effectiveness of laparoscopic surgery for stomach and colon cancer, which are not inferior to open surgery, have been proven by numerous large-scale randomized controlled trials [16,35,45], and therefore the introduction of these possibilities into the surgery of injuries of these organs does not seem difficult. Di Saverio et al. the results of laparoscopic elimination of injuries of the small and large intestines and their mesentery by applying double-layer sutures to the intestinal wall or by resection and intracorporeal or extracorporeal application of interstitial anastomosis with larger defects were described. New devices for hemostasis contribute to improving the efficiency of laparoscopy in case of damage to mesentery vessels [24]. In another, earlier, article, the same author reports on the successful performance of laparoscopic resection of the colon according to Hartmann, performed for traumatic injury [23]. But, at the same time, the possibilities and safety issues of laparoscopic surgery of injuries of retroperitoneal organs, especially the duodenum and pancreas, remain a subject of discussion. It is known that laparoscopic access to retroperitoneal organs requires more experience and skills of a surgeon than other approaches in bowel surgery. In recent years, a number of meta-analyses on laparoscopic pancreatic surgery have been published, but there are no indications of randomized controlled trials [17,31,42].

According to the results of a meta-analysis of 8 observational studies and 1 randomized clinical trial, laparoscopic interventions in abdominal injuries contribute to a decrease in the frequency of wound complications and pneumonia [29].

In addition, the duration of the operation and the terms of inpatient treatment with therapeutic laparoscopy are noticeably shorter compared to laparotomy interventions both in patients with wounds and in patients with closed abdominal trauma [20,30,37,39,40,41]. So, S.Hajibandeh et al. It is indicated that the average duration of laparoscopy for intestinal injury is 52 minutes versus 80 minutes for laparotomy ($p=0.0003$) [20]. In three studies comparing the duration of inpatient treatment in groups of patients undergoing laparoscopy and laparotomy, it varied, respectively, from 3 to 11 days after laparoscopy and from 8 to 21 days after laparotomy [15,37,39].

Among the contraindications to laparoscopy for abdominal injuries, first of all, the serious condition of the patient and purulent peritonitis are indicated. However, some clinicians have begun to expand these boundaries in recent years. In particular, S.Di Saverio et al. they report excellent results of laparoscopic interventions performed against the background of conditions previously considered absolute contraindications – diffuse peritonitis and adhesive disease [1]. It should be pointed out that such publications should be treated with caution due to the small number of observations and inconsistency of the results, and they can only be taken into account by experienced laparoscopic surgeons. Due to the lack of necessary randomized controlled trials, the level of evidence of recommendations for the use of endovideosurgical techniques in patients with abdominal trauma is ranked as "weak" in current clinical protocols [21,44].

Conclusion

The use of laparoscopy in patients with isolated and combined abdominal injuries is of increasing interest to surgeons in modern surgery. In our opinion, the degree of study of the use of laparoscopy in surgery of abdominal injuries clearly reflects the recent R.Cirocchi et al.[19] systematic review and meta-analysis of publications for the period from 1990 to 2016. This review included the results of 9817 laparoscopies for abdominal trauma. The average conversion rate is 26.2%. Against the background of improved methods of radiation diagnostics, wider use of endovideosurgical and interventional technologies, the frequency of therapeutic procedures for wide laparotomy decreased from 69% to 47.5%, while the frequency of therapeutic laparoscopies increased from 7.2% to 22.7%. Overall perioperative mortality was significantly lower in the laparoscopy group [95%CI 0.35 (0.26-0.48)]. In the same group, the duration of inpatient treatment was also significantly shorter [95%CI -3.48 (-8.91 to 1.96)]. Nevertheless, the authors of the review indicate that there is a steady trend towards a significant decrease in the use of laparoscopy in patients with abdominal trauma, which they associate with the widespread use of radiation (including interventional) imaging methods, which allows to specify the indications for diagnostic laparoscopy.

More accurate preoperative diagnosis of the volume and nature of intra-abdominal injuries in combination with the diagnostic capabilities of laparoscopy contributed to a noticeable decrease in the frequency of futile (diagnostic) laparotomies. The reports available in the literature on the growing trend in the use of therapeutic possibilities of laparoscopy, however, do not allow us to draw an unambiguous conclusion about the safety and effectiveness of the method due to the small number of observations included in published studies, the poor quality of the studies conducted, the retrospective observational nature of the studies (low level of evidence), the presence of a high risk of subjectivity and high heterogeneity of the results obtained by individual authors. results.

In addition, despite all the obvious advantages of using laparoscopy for abdominal injuries, still, according to most experts, it is applicable in patients with stable hemodynamics. Thus, it becomes obvious the necessity, prospects and relevance of further studies to evaluate the results of the use of laparoscopic techniques in patients with abdominal injuries, mainly in patients with closed abdominal trauma.

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